

Supporting Information

Figure S1: Thickness distribution histograms of WS₂ obtained from SEM image.

Figure S2: Photodetector response of 125 on/off cycles.

Figure S3: Dependence of response time of the device with different input power.

Figure S4: Photocurrent vs power density at different regimes of incident power ($V_{\text{bias}}=5\text{V}$). The red line is the fitting results.

Figure S5: The photocurrent response of the WS₂ photodetector on water-soluble paper at different light power and bias voltage ($\lambda=660\text{nm}$).

Figure S6: Spectral response of the WS₂ photodetector on soluble paper. (a) time-resolved photoresponse of the device under illumination at varying wavelengths (from 470nm to 740nm) with 0.30 mW power, (b) variation of responsivity with the different wavelength of light at 5V bias voltage.

Figure S7: Strain-dependent measurement of WS₂-on-paper devices. (a) I-V characteristics of the device under different applied strain levels (0% to 0.44%). The inset shows an optical image of the bending setup used to apply strain. (b) Relative resistance change ($\Delta R/R_0$) as a function of strain for applied voltages of $\pm 5V$. The gauge factor (GF) is obtained from a linear fit.

Figure S8: Raman spectra of abraded WS₂ device. Raman spectra obtained from. (a) the WS₂ device on soluble paper, (b) the filter paper after dissolving the device in water and vacuum filtering. The inset shows optical microscopy image of the WS₂ film on soluble paper and filter paper.

Figure S9: EDX spectrum of WS₂ (a) on soluble paper and (b) on filter paper after vacuum filtering. The inset images show SEM images of WS₂ on soluble paper and filter paper, respectively.